

TEACHING: THE LAW OF LARGE NUMBERS, LOGICAL THINKING.

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Annotation.

the article deals with how to improve the ability of students' logical thinking based on simplicity, accessibility, including the practical meanings of topics and concepts.

Keywords.

stability, event, mathematical expectation, probability, test, frequency, learning, accessibility, law of large numbers.

Entrance department.

Each subject has its own task and specific characteristics in teaching. In education, the main form of science teaching is classroom training. However, since the lessons are limited, it is not possible to fully cover the subject. Nevertheless, it is necessary to achieve the formation of a complete picture of the science, its goals and tasks in the students during the training.

Mathematical education, that is, teaching, is a complex process that depends on many aspects. It can be said that one of the aspects and the most important one is logical thinking. In this regard, the development of students' ability to think logically remains the main goal. That is why it is necessary to strengthen proof skills in students. After all, "proof" is the basis of logical thinking. It is necessary to convince the reader of a feature presented within the topic. Simplicity, logical connection, and coherence are also important in the statement.

Department of Methods

No matter what the topic is, it is necessary to follow the principles of simplicity and interest in the statement, as well as creating an opportunity for students to think independently during the statement of the topic.

For example, what should be emphasized in the example of the topic of the law of large numbers? First of all, it is necessary to explain the main content of this law - its essence, its applications, and its practical significance.

It is impossible to say with certainty what value a random variable will take as a result of an experiment. It depends on many random factors that it is impossible to account for all of them. But in fact it is not like that. It turns out that, based on

some broader conditions, in a set of a sufficiently large number of random variables, they almost lose their randomness and begin to gain legitimacy.

In practice, it is important to know under what conditions the character of randomness of a large number of random variables acquires legitimacy. Due to such conditions, a large number of random variables almost lose their randomness, and can make it possible to make preliminary conclusions about how the processes will proceed.

Such conditions are reflected in Chebyshev's, Bernoulli's and other theorems called the law of large numbers.

Almost all topics, concepts, theorems, properties are the result of logical thinking.

It should be noted that Bernoulli's, Lyapunov's, Chebyshev's and Laplace's theorems form a law called the law of large numbers.

Random quantities often occur in measurements in most applications, and the measurements themselves are inherently error-prone.

Results section

It is known that individual measurement results $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n$ can have stronger dispersion, but at the same time their arithmetic mean $\frac{1}{n}(\xi_1 + \xi_2 + \dots + \xi_n)$ has more stability will be In other words, the level of stagnation increases in the sum of individual random quantities.

Below is a case of Chebyshev's theorem, which is one of the most famous theorems in this category:

If $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n$ are not related to pairs of random variables and their mathematical expectations are the same, i.e. $M(\xi_1) = M(\xi_2) = \dots = M(\xi_n) = a$, then for any $\varepsilon > 0$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$ the following probability inequality holds [2]

$$P \left\{ \left| \frac{\xi_1 + \xi_2 + \dots + \xi_n}{n} - a \right| > \varepsilon \right\} \rightarrow 0.$$

Discussion.

We do not want to dwell here on these and other similar theorems, but we want to think about the general importance of the law of large numbers, its practical features, which may help readers to understand the topic more deeply. Simply put, the essence of this law is that as the number of experiments of random variables increases, their random nature tends to become more regular. In this regard, you can give a number of factual examples to make it more understandable for students:

1. Results of observations on the frequency of tails in a series of 1000 coin tosses (10 series): 501, 485, 509, 536, 485, 488, 500, 497, 494, 484 [3].

2. De Mere's game. An ardent gambler, French de Mere invented a unique game in order to win more. He always began to bet on at least one coat of arms out of four rolls of the dice. His intuition (farosati) did not warn. Below are the results of his acquaintance, the French mathematician Pascal, who studied the game:

The game cube has six sides and the numbers 1,2,3,4,5,6 are written on them. One of these points can be randomly dropped when the cube is thrown. All these six cases are equally likely, and the probability of one of them, for example, 6 points, can be taken as $1/6$. Also, when two dice are thrown, the number of such equally possible cases (events) is $6*6=36$, and among them at least one six point can fall in 11 cases. So, de Mere's chance to win is $11/36$. The probability of landing at least one six when the number of cubes is three is $91/216$, the same indicator is $671/1296$ for four cubes. Now let's pay attention to the following: $\frac{11}{36} < \frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{91}{216} < \frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{671}{1296} > \frac{1}{2}$!

Of course, this is why it is understandable that de Mere always wins when the number of games is large when four dice are thrown.

3. According to Swedish statistics, it is known that the relative frequency of female births during a certain year is characterized by the following numbers for months: 0.486; 0.489; 0.490; 0.471; 0.478; 0.482; 0.462; 0.484; 0.485; 0.491; 0.482; 0.473.

4. Many coin tossing experiments were conducted, the heads were counted and the following results were obtained:

According to the number of coin tosses 4040, 12000 and 24000, the relative frequencies of corresponding coat of arms are 0.5069, respectively; It is known that it is 0.5016 and 0.5005.

All examples show that the respective relative frequencies are observed to oscillate around their respective probabilities (around $1/2$ in these examples).

Conclusion.

Such examples are very useful in presenting students with the basic concepts of probability theory, as well as in explaining the law of large numbers. For this and similar additional information, see: [1-6].

There are processes in which the law of large numbers is directly reflected. The more people unite and act in an organized manner, the higher their success rate will be.

The following message was published in the press. In a small Chinese city, all its fifteen thousand residents gathered all their money and engaged in business,

and in a short time, a personal account number was opened for each citizen of the city, and hundreds of thousands of dollars were transferred.

Many such examples can be given. It should be said that the main goal is to convey topics to students and even students of non-mathematical specialties, based on the principles of simplicity and interest, showing their practical importance.

It can be seen that the echo of this law can be observed on a large scale in marriage.

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